

Phytochemical profiling and Membrane stabilization based in vitro Anti-Inflammatory activity of *Rothia indica* Root and Fruit extracts

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Abstract:

Inflammation is a multifaceted defensive mechanism that arises due to oxidative damage and the presence of inflammatory mediators. Plant-derived secondary metabolites are gaining recognition as safe and effective anti-inflammatory agents. The genus *Rothia* (Fabaceae), with only two species, remains pharmacologically underexplored. This study analyzed the qualitative and quantitative phytochemical profiles of *Rothia indica* root and fruit extracts (petroleum ether, ethyl acetate, ethanol, aqueous) and assessed their in vitro anti-inflammatory activity via the Human Red Blood Cell (HRBC) membrane stabilization assay. Phenolics, flavonoids, tannins, and saponins were detected mainly in polar and semi-polar extracts. The ethanol fruit extract had the highest phenolic (239.84 ± 3.7 mg GAE/g) and tannin (188.3 ± 3.4 mg GAE/g) contents, followed by ethyl acetate extracts, which showed the highest flavonoid levels in root and fruit (221.36 ± 2.8 and 205.32 ± 3.9 mg RE/g). Petroleum ether extracts had the lowest phytochemical content. In the heat-induced hemolysis assay, the ethanol fruit extract exhibited significant membrane stabilization ($IC_{50} = 27.04$ μ g/ml). Both fruit and root ethanol extracts showed concentration-dependent inhibition in hypotonic solution-induced hemolysis, with maximum inhibitions of 85.61 ± 0.77 mg/ml and 83.95 ± 0.43 mg/ml, respectively. These results provide the first in vitro evidence of *Rothia indica*'s membrane-stabilizing anti-inflammatory activity and support further in vivo and pharmacological studies.

Keywords: *Rothia indica*, Root and Fruit extracts, phytochemical analysis; Membrane Stabilization; in vitro anti-inflammatory activity.

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Introduction:

Inflammation is a complex biological response initiated by tissue injury, infection, or immunological stimuli characterized by edema, redness, and localized pain. It encompasses

physiological changes such as the release of hydrolytic enzymes, vasodilation, increased vascular permeability, elevated blood pressure, and fluid extravasation, which contribute to tissue damage and repair (Yesmi *et al.*, 2020). Inflammatory reactions also activate immune cells and produce free radicals, intensifying tissue injury and lipid peroxidation (Kumar *et al.* 2012, Chirumamilla & Taduri 2023). Given inflammation's role in various diseases, pharmaceutical research focuses on developing safer, more effective anti-inflammatory agents. India's rich ethno-botanical heritage includes many medicinal plants traditionally used for pain and inflammation (Soorya *et al.*, 2023), yet many lack rigorous scientific validation (Bairagi *et al.*, 2023). This necessitates systematic research to confirm their therapeutic potential and aid novel anti-inflammatory drug development from natural sources.

The Fabaceae family is the third-largest family of higher plants in the plant kingdom, consisting primarily of flowering plants, including legumes, peas, trees, shrubs, and herbs (Grygier *et al.*, 2022). These plants exhibit broad ecological adaptability, thriving across diverse climatic and environmental conditions throughout Africa and Asia (Frimpong *et al.*, 2021). Traditional medicine remains a vital component of primary healthcare in these regions, with Fabaceae species frequently utilized due to their rich bioactive phytochemicals (Auditeau *et al.*, 2019). Phytochemical studies have identified various secondary metabolites such as alkaloids, flavonoids, saponins, tannins, steroids, and terpenoids in multiple plant parts, including leaves, bark, stems, roots, and fruits, highlighting their potential in drug discovery and therapeutic development. These compounds demonstrate significant biological activities, including anti-inflammatory, anticancer, antibacterial, antimalarial, and antioxidant effects (Sowe *et al.*, 2025). Moreover, quantitative assessments of total phenolic and flavonoid contents are considered reliable predictors of biological efficacy, with strong correlations observed between polyphenol levels and anti-inflammatory activity (Sidhic *et al.*, 2023).

The genus *Rothia* (Fabaceae) is taxonomically restricted and contains only two known species, *Rothia indica* and *Rothia hirsute* (Boatwright *et al.* 2008). Despite this limited species diversity, scientific investigations on the phytochemical composition and pharmacological properties of *Rothia* remain extremely scarce. Erythrocyte membranes resemble lysosomal membranes; Membrane stabilization is a key anti-inflammatory mechanism, as it inhibits lysosomal mediator release. HRBC membrane stabilization assays a common in vitro method to evaluate anti-inflammatory activity by preventing the release of inflammatory mediators and enzymes (Aourahoun *et al.*, 2019). No prior studies have examined the anti-inflammatory effects of

Rothia indica roots and fruits. This study systematically analyzes their phytochemical composition and in vitro anti-inflammatory potential, establishing a basis for their medicinal value.

Materials and methods

Preparation of plant extracts:

Rothia indica roots and fruits were collected from agricultural land in Onnapalayam village, a foothill region on Siruvani Scheme Road, Coimbatore. The samples were washed thoroughly in running tap water, shade-dried, and grinded. A Soxhlet extraction system was used to extract the biochemical. The solvents selected based on their polarity included petroleum ether, ethyl acetate, ethanol, and aqueous. The collected extracts were dried using a rotary evaporator at 38° C and 120 rpm. After the solvent evaporated, the solid residue, which was utilized for further analysis, was kept at 4° C until.

Qualitative phytochemical screening:

Evaluation of Secondary metabolites:

Petroleum ether, ethyl acetate, Ethanol and Aqueous extracts of *Rothia indica* Root and Fruit were analyzed qualitatively to detect the presence and absence of phytochemicals. The presence of alkaloids was determined using Dragendroff's, Hager's, and Wagner's tests, and flavonoids were determined using 10% HCL and 5% NaOH. Phenolic content was determined using the ferric chloride test. Tannin was tested using the lead subacetate test. Steroids were analyzed using the Liebermann–test. Triterpenoids were identified using the Liebermann–Burchard test, and cardiac glycosides were identified using the Keller–Killiani test. Gum and mucilages were tested using alcohol. Fixed oils and fats were tested using the spot test. Anthraquinones using Borntrager's test. Saponins by foam test.

Quantitative Determination of Phytochemical Constituents

Total Phenolic content (TPC):

The total phenol content was determined using the Folin-Ciocalteu method described by Makkar (2003) with slight modifications. The plant extract (100 µL) was diluted to 1 ml by adding 900 µL of distilled water. One milliliter of distilled water was used as a blank. Next, 500 µl of Folin-Ciocalteu reagent (1N) was added to all the test tubes, including the blank. After 5 min of incubation, 2.5 ml of 5% Na₂CO₃ (Sodium carbonate) solution was added. After

vortexing the reaction mixture, the test tubes were placed in the dark for 40 min. The formation of blue color in the incubated test tubes indicated the presence of phenolics. The absorbance was measured at 725 nm against a blank reagent. Gallic acid was used as the standard, and the results were expressed as mg GAE/g extract.

Total Tannin content (TTC):

Tannin content was estimated using the PVPP precipitation method, as described by Makkar (2003). 500 µl of plant extract was mixed with 100 mg of polyvinylpolypyrrolidone (PVPP) and 1 ml of distilled water, vortexed thoroughly, and incubated at 4° C for 15 min. The mixture was centrifuged at 4000 rpm for 10 min, and the supernatant was collected. The supernatant contained only non-tannin phenolics, as the tannins were precipitated along with PVPP. The phenolic content of the supernatant was measured and expressed as the content of non-tannin phenolics and expressed as mg GAE/g of extract.

Total Flavonoid content (TFC):

The total flavonoid content (TFC) was determined with minor modifications based on the procedure described by Zhishenet *et al.* (1999). A test tube containing 2.5 ml distilled water served as a blank (except for the plant extract, all solutions were added). Briefly, 800 µL of plant extract was mixed with 1.7 ml of distilled water, followed by the addition of 150 µL of 5% NaNO₂ (Sodium Nitrate). Then 150µl of 10% AlCl₃ was added to all tubes, including the blank. After 6 min of incubation at room temperature, 4.8 ml of 4% NaOH was added, which was made up to 5 ml using distilled water and allowed to stand for 15 min. Pink color formation due to the presence of flavonoids. The reaction mixture was thoroughly mixed, and the absorbance was measured at 510 nm. Rutin was used as a standard and expressed as mg/RE (rutin equivalents)/g extract.

In vitro Anti-inflammatory activity:

Membrane Stabilization Assay:

In vitro assays are predominantly cell- or protein-based, offering rapid, simple, and cost-effective evaluations. Moreover, in vitro models assist in elucidating the molecular mechanisms of the bioactive compounds responsible for their anti-inflammatory activity (Dzoyem *et al.*, 2017). Among the available methods, the red blood cell (RBC) membrane stabilization assay is one of the most extensively utilized screening methods for assessing anti-inflammatory potential (Akhtar 2022).

Preparation of erythrocyte suspension:

Whole blood was collected from healthy human volunteers under standard laboratory conditions. The blood sample was mixed with an equal volume of sterile Alsever's solution. The collected blood samples were washed three times with an isotonic saline solution (0.9% NaCl) to remove plasma and other components. A 10% v/v erythrocyte suspension was prepared using isotonic saline and phosphate buffers. The suspension was centrifuged at 3000 rpm for 10 min, and the resulting erythrocyte pellet was re-suspended to obtain a stock erythrocyte suspension for further analysis. The procedure was performed according to previously reported methods (Hafeez *et al.*, 2022; Chirumamilla and Taduri, 2023).

Heat-induced hemolysis assay:

The reaction mixture was prepared by incubating a 100 µL RBC suspension and 3 ml of phosphate-buffered saline with *Rothia indica* root and fruit extracts at concentrations of 50, 100, 150, 200, and 250 µg/ml, prepared in petroleum ether, ethyl acetate, ethanol, and aqueous. The control was maintained by replacing the extract with isosaline. Diclofenac was used as the reference standard in separate reaction tube. All reactions, including the control, were incubated in a water bath at 54° C for 20 min. The sample was then centrifuged at 2500 rpm for 5 min, and the absorbance of the supernatant was measured at 540 nm. With few tweaks, the approach of Fathima *et al.* (2024) was used. The extent of hemolysis was determined by comparing the absorbance values of the treated samples with those of the control.

$$\% \text{ inhibition of haemolysis} = \frac{\{\text{Absorbance of control} - \text{Absorbance of sample}\}}{\{\text{Absorbance of control}\}} \times 100$$

Hypotonic solution-induced hemolysis

For the assay, 1 ml of *Rothia indica* root and fruit extract was combined with 1 ml of phosphate buffer (pH 7.4), 0.5 ml of RBC suspension, and 2 ml of hyposaline solution. The reaction mixture was incubated at 37 °C for 30 min, followed by centrifugation at 3000 rpm for 10 min. The absorbance of the resulting supernatant was measured at 560 nm using a spectrophotometer (Chirumamilla and Taduri 2023). Diclofenac was used as the reference standard (Gupta *et al.* 2021). The control group was treated with all the components of the assay mixture, excluding the test sample. Hemolysis in the control sample was considered as 100% (Yesmin *et al.* 2020), and the percentage inhibition of hemolysis (percentage of protection) were evaluated using the formula

$$\text{Percentage protection} = 100 - \frac{\{\text{Absorbance of test sample}\}}{\{\text{Absorbance of control}\}} \times 100$$

Statistical analysis

All experiments were carried out in triplicates, and the results were expressed as mean±standard deviation (SD). The statistical analysis was performed using IBM SPSS Statistics version 23.0. The effects of different plant parts and solvent extracts were analysed using Two-way Anova. Post hoc comparison of means was performed using Tukey's HSD test. Differences between groups were considered statistically significant at $p < 0.01$ and $p < 0.001$ levels.

Result and discussion

Qualitative analysis:

Phytochemical analysis is essential for evaluating the potential medicinal properties of plants and identifying the bioactive constituents responsible for their documented biological activity. This study also establishes a basis for the targeted isolation of compounds and facilitates more comprehensive investigations. The effectiveness of phytochemical extraction is significantly influenced by the nature of the solvent used, while analytical tests are employed to ascertain the specific phytochemical content within the sample (Shaikh and Patil 2020). Qualitative phytochemical screening of Petroleum Ether, Ethyl Acetate, Ethanol, and Aqueous extracts revealed the presence and absence of secondary metabolites (**Table 1**). Anthraquinones, fixed oils, gums, mucilage, and cardioglycosides were not detected in any of the extracts. Alkaloids, Flavonoids, Phenolic compounds, and tannins were predominantly present in the ethyl acetate, ethanol, and aqueous extracts. Ethanol exhibited a stronger positive reaction, which was attributed to its intermediate polarity, which facilitated the extraction of both polar and moderately polar compounds. Terpenoids and steroids were detected in the ethanol and ethyl acetate extracts, whereas the petroleum ether extracts showed negligible phytochemicals. Saponins were exclusively observed in the ethanol extract of *Rothia indica* root extract. The metabolite groups are well known for their function in influencing oxidative stress and inflammatory pathways in many medicinal plants, particularly those of the Fabaceae family (Rahman & Hossen 2025; Gonfa *et al* 2023).

Table 1: Qualitative phytochemical screening of *Rothia indica* root and fruit extracts

s.no	Chemical constituent	Tests	Organic solvent						AQ	
			PE		EA		ET		R.R	R.F
			R.R	R.F	R.R	R.F	R.R	R.F		
1	Alkaloids	a) Dragendorff's test	-	-	-	+	-	++	-	++
		b) Mayer's test	-	-	-	+	-	+	-	+
		c) Wagner's test	-	-	-	-	-	+	-	-
2	Flavonoids	10% HCL & 5% NAOH test	-	-	+++	++	+++	+++	+++	+++
3	Phenolics	5% FeCl ₃ test	-	-	++	+++	+	+++	+	++
4	Tannin	Lead sub acetate test	-	-	-	+	+++	+++	+++	++
5	Steroids	Liebermann-Burchard's test	-	-	-	-	+	-	+	-
6	Terpenoids	a) Liebermann-Burchard's test	+	-	+++	-	++	-	+	-
		b) Salkowski's test	++	-	+	-	++	-	-	-
7	Saponins	Foam test	-	-	-	-	+++	-	-	-
8	Cardiac-Glycosides	Keller-Kiliani test	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
9	Gum & Mucilages	Whistler & BeMiller test	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
10	Fixed oils	Spot test	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
11	Anthraquinones	Sanker and Nahar test	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-

PE-Petroleum Ether; EA- Ethyl Acetate; ET- Ethanol; AQ- Aqueous; RR- *Rothia indica* Root; RF- *Rothia indica* Fruit; (+) Present; (-) Absent.

Plants containing flavonoids exhibit a wide range of bioactivities, including antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, hepatoprotective, anti-cancer, anti-viral, and anti-allergic effects (Neil *et al.*, 2000). Additionally, these compounds act as platelet aggregation inhibitors, contributing to

cardiovascular health (Okwu and Emenike 2006). Phenolic compounds further enhance the therapeutic potential of plants by exerting anti-inflammatory effects through the inhibition of enzymes responsible for inflammation and disease progression (Okwu 2004). They also function as immune enhancers and hormone modulators, supporting overall physiological balance (Okwu and Omodamino 2005). Plants that contain tannin could be used as astringent and haemostatic properties that aid wound healing and reduce mucosal inflammation. They are also recognized as potent antioxidants (Ibitoye 2003; Ajuru *et al* 2017). Saponins demonstrate expectorant activity beneficial in managing upper respiratory tract inflammation and possess diverse pharmacological properties such as anti-diabetic, anti-fungal, immune modulatory, anti-cancer, and cholesterol-lowering effects (Jimoh and Oladji 2005). The presence and enrichment of polyphenolic compounds in ethanol and aqueous extracts highlight their significant contribution to antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, anticancer, and antimicrobial activities. Collectively, these findings validate the use of ethanol as an effective solvent for extracting bioactive constituents from the studied plant material, ensuring the retention of compounds with substantial therapeutic potential.

Quantification assays:

Total Phenolic content:

The quantification of total phenolic content in different extracts of *Rothia indica* fruit and root using the Folin-Ciocalteu reagent method. The use of a calibration curve ($Y=0.0109X + 0.0119$; $R^2 = 0.9919$) based on gallic acid allows for standardized measurement, expressed as mg GAE/g extract, which is a common and reliable approach in phenolic content analysis. The data indicate that the ethanol extract of the fruit contains the highest phenolic concentration (239.84 ± 3.7 mg GAE/g), suggesting that ethanol is an effective solvent for extracting phenolic compounds from the fruit. The ethyl acetate extracts of both fruit and root also show substantial phenolic content, though lower than the ethanol fruit extract (165.22 ± 3.3 & 167.9 ± 0.9 mg GAE/g extract). This solvent-dependent variation highlights the importance of solvent polarity in extracting phenolics, with ethanol and ethyl acetate being more efficient than water in some cases. Notably, the fruit extracts generally have higher phenolic content than root extracts, especially in ethanol and water solvents. The water extract of the fruit shows a phenolic content nearly three times greater than that of the root, indicating that the fruit contains more water-soluble antioxidants. This suggests that the fruit may have a richer profile of hydrophilic phenolic compounds compared to the root, which could be relevant for antioxidant activity and potential health benefits (Chang *et al.*, 2001; Karthikkumaran & Vasanthakumari 2023).

Total Tannin content:

Tannins are water-soluble polyphenols found in many fruits (Karthikkumar & Vasanthakumari 2023). The TTC of *Rothia indica* fruit and root extracts is presented in **Table 2**. The tannin content was calculated using a gallic acid calibration curve ($y=0.0109+0.0119x$; $R^2=0.9919$) and expressed as mg gallic acid equivalent (GAE) per gram of extract. The results revealed marked variations depending on the plant parts and solvents used. The ethanol extract of the fruit exhibited a significantly higher tannin content (188.37 ± 3.4 mg GAE/g extract) than that of the root (88.99 ± 3.9 mg GAE/g extract), indicating nearly a two-fold increase in the fruit. The aqueous extract showed higher tannin levels in the fruit than in the root (78.28 ± 2.9 & 30.88 ± 3.8 mg GAE/g extract). The tannin content in the Petroleum ether extract was higher in the fruit than in the root, although the overall concentrations were low in both parts. However, the ethyl acetate extract showed a higher tannin content in the root (83.18 ± 1 mg GAE/g extract) than in the fruit (72.47 ± 3.9 mg GAE/g extract).

Total Flavonoid content:

Flavonoids are the most ubiquitous and extensively distributed plant phenolic compounds, and their hydroxyl groups confer scavenging activity, making them particularly potent antioxidants and anti-inflammatory agents. Plant flavonoids are well-known natural antioxidants (Darmany et al., 1998). The results were expressed as rutin standard equivalents ($y=0.0113x+0.0039$; $R^2=0.9967$), as rutin is a key flavonoid found in many plants. The total flavonoid content was highest in the ethyl acetate extracts for both samples, reaching 221.36 ± 2.8 mg RE/g extract in the roots and 205.32 ± 3.9 mg RE/g extract in the fruit. Petroleum ether yielded the lowest results for both plant parts. Notably, the fruit showed nearly double the flavonoid concentration of the root when extracted with water (100.93 ± 0.27 mg RE/g extract; 48.9 ± 0.5 mg RE/g extract), as indicated in **Table 2**.

Phenolic acids from medicinal and edible homologous plants exhibit notable anti-inflammatory activity, as evidenced by numerous studies on inflammatory diseases (Iloki et al, 2015). The extractability of phenolic and polyphenolic compounds is influenced by the polarity of the solvent and solute-to-solvent interactions. Polar and semi-polar solvents are more effective at extracting phenolic compounds. These results suggest that ethyl acetate and ethanol are more effective solvents for recovering bioactive compounds from the roots and fruit of *Rothia indica*. While the fruit appears to be the superior source of total phenolics and tannins, the root contains significantly higher quantities of flavonoids in semi-polar solvents. Variation in phytochemical

composition among different plant parts may be attributed to gene expression, which affects antioxidant and other biological activities (Febriani *et al.*, 2020). Overall, solvent polarity plays a key role in maximizing polyphenol recovery and guiding the appropriate solvent selection (Ghasemzadeh *et al.*, 2011).

Table 2: Total Phenolic, Tannin and Flavonoid Content of *Rothia indica* root and fruit extracts

Extracts	Total Phenolic Content (mg GAE/g Extract)		Total Tannin Content (mg GAE/g Extract)		Total Flavonoid Content (mg RE/g Extract)	
	Root 100 µl	Fruit 100 µl	Root 500 µl	Fruit 500 µl	Root 800 µl	Fruit 800 µl
Petroleum ether	70.42 ± 1.9	35.56 ± 2.3	21.71 ± 3.7	31.49 ± 2.3	20.51 ± 0.89	14.83 ± 1.1
Ethyl acetate	167.98 ± 0.9	165.22 ± 3.3	83.18 ± 1	72.47 ± 3.9	221.36 ± 2.8	205.32 ± 3.9
Ethanol	149.9 ± 3.4	239.84 ± 3.7	88.99 ± 3.9	188.3 ± 3.4	86.62 ± 1.3	97.35 ± 0.67
Water	49.32 ± 1.4	141.98 ± 2.8	30.88 ± 3.8	78.28 ± 2.9	48.9 ± 0.5	100.9 ± 0.27

Results are shown as mean ± SD of triplicate analyses (n=3)

Statistical analysis was performed for TPC, TTC and TFC using Two-way ANOVA, and differences were considered highly significantly at $p < 0.001$ according to Tukey's HSD test.

GAE- Gallic Acid Equivalents; RE- Rutin Equivalents

Anti-inflammatory:

Heat-induced hemolysis:

The in vitro anti-inflammatory activity of different solvent extracts of the roots and fruits were evaluated using a heat-induced hemolysis assay. The activity was assessed based on the percentage inhibition at five different concentrations and expressed as IC₅₀ values (µg/ml), as shown in **Figure 1**. Overall, the fruit extracts exhibited higher anti-inflammatory activity than the root extracts across all four solvents, as evidenced by their lower IC₅₀ Values. Among the extracts tested, the ethanol extract of the fruit showed the lowest IC₅₀ value (27.04 µg/ml), indicating the highest activity. This was followed by ethyl acetate (33.34 µg/ml). Petroleum

ether and aqueous extracts showed comparatively lower activity, with IC₅₀ values above 50 µg/ml. The root extract showed relatively higher IC₅₀ values than the fruit extract, indicating that it has lower activity than the fruit extract. The standard drug diclofenac exhibited the highest inhibition of hemolysis, with an IC₅₀ value of 17.89 µg/ml.

Figure 1: Dose-dependent inhibition of heat induced hemolysis by different extracts at concentration of (50, 100, 150, 200, and 250 µg/ml). IC₅₀ values were calculated from the concentration response curve. Results are shown as mean ± SD of triplicate analyses (n=3). Statistical analysis was performed using Two-way ANOVA, and differences were considered highly significantly at p < 0.001 according to Tukey's HSD test.

Hypotonic-induced hemolysis:

The anti-inflammatory activity of *Rothia indica* root and fruit extracts was evaluated using a hypotonic-induced hemolysis assay. The assay was performed using 1 ml (1000 mg/ml) of the extract. The activity was expressed as the percentage inhibition of hemolysis at the tested concentration, and the results are presented as the mean ± SD of triplicate analyses (**Figure. 2**). Among the tested extracts, the ethanol fraction exhibited the highest membrane-stabilizing effect in both parts. The ethanol extract of the fruit showed the highest percentage of inhibition (85.61 ± 0.77 %) compared to the corresponding root extract (83.95 ± 0.43 %). The aqueous extract showed appreciable activity, exhibiting higher inhibition in the fruit than in the root extract (79.2 ± 0.78 % and 76.64 ± 0.9 %, respectively). The ethyl acetate extract showed moderate inhibition, with the fruit and root extracts showing 61.98 ± 0.26 % and 62.03 ± 1.63 % inhibition, respectively. The petroleum ether extract exhibited the lowest membrane

stabilization activity. The standard drug diclofenac exhibited the highest inhibition of hemolysis (91.14 ± 0.42 %).

Figure 2: Percentage inhibition of hypotonic solution-induced hemolysis by different extracts at a concentration of 1 ml. Results are shown as mean \pm SD of triplicate analyses (n=3). Statistical analysis was performed using Two-way ANOVA ($p < 0.01$) according to Tukey's HSD test.

The membrane stabilization assay, an established in vitro model for assessing anti-inflammatory activity, showed that *Rothia indica* extracts significantly inhibit heat- and hypotonicity-induced hemolysis, indicating strong membrane-protective and anti-inflammatory potential. Fruit extracts, especially ethanol and ethyl acetate fractions, demonstrated the highest inhibition, likely due to phenolic and polyphenolic compounds such as flavonoids and tannins. These compounds modulate inflammation by inhibiting pro-inflammatory enzymes, scavenging reactive species, and regulating cytokines (Sidhic *et al.* 2023). According to reviews phytochemistry of Fabaceae family plants, flavonoids, pterocarpan, and tannins frequently work together to improve antioxidant defense systems also modifies inflammatory signaling pathways (Rahman & Hossen 2025; Usman *et al.*, 2022). The phytochemical diversity in *Rothia indica* aligns with findings in other Fabaceae species, supporting its biological efficacy. Although limited to in vitro tests at a fixed concentration, the results endorse *Rothia indica* anti-inflammatory potential through membrane stabilization.

Conclusion:

In summary, the findings from this study highlight the promising anti-inflammatory potential of *Rothia indica* root and fruit extracts, supported by their rich phytochemical profiles and significant membrane stabilization activity. These in vitro results provide a foundational understanding of the extracts' bioactive properties, particularly their capacity to protect cellular membranes and modulate inflammatory processes. To fully establish their therapeutic value, further investigations using in vivo models and targeted isolation of active constituents are necessary to validate efficacy and clarify the precise mechanisms involved.

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